

ODONTOGENIC OSTEOMYELITIS OF THE JAWS IN CHILDREN**Abdumutalipova M. A.**

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Abstract

Odontogenic osteomyelitis is an inflammatory disease of the jawbone caused by tooth-related infections. It is one of the most common infectious bone diseases in children. The peculiarities of its course are associated with the physiological characteristics of a child's body and the immaturity of their immune system. Due to the active development of deciduous and permanent teeth in children, the risk of developing osteomyelitis is significantly higher. This article provides a detailed overview of the clinical manifestations, diagnostic approaches, and modern treatment methods for this condition.

Keywords: odontogenic osteomyelitis, pediatric dentistry, jaw inflammation, bone infection, diagnostics, treatment.

Bolalarda jag'larning odontogen osteomiyeliti**Saparbayev M., Abdumutalipova M. A.**

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Kirish

Odontogen osteomiyelit — bu jag' suyaklarining tishlardan kelib chiqadigan yallig'lanishi bo'lib, bolalar o'rtasida eng ko'p uchraydigan yuqumli suyak kasalliklaridan biridir. Kasallikning o'ziga xos kechishi bolalar organizmining fiziologik xususiyatlari va immun tizimining yetishmasligi bilan bog'liq. Bolalarda sut va doimiy tishlar rivojlanishidagi jarayonlarning aktivligi sababli osteomiyelitning rivojlanish xavfi yuqori. Ushbu maqolada kasallikning klinik ko'rinishlari, diagnostik yondashuvlari va zamonaviy davolash usullari haqida batafsil ma'lumot beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: odontogen osteomiyelit bolalar stomatologiyasi, jag' yallig'lanishi, suyak infeksiyasi, diagnostika, davolash.

ОДОНТОГЕННЫЙ ОСТЕОМИЕЛИТ ЧЕЛЮСТЕЙ У ДЕТЕЙ

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Аннотация

Одонтогенный остеомиелит — это воспалительное заболевание челюстной кости, вызванное инфекцией, исходящей из зубов. Это одно из наиболее распространенных инфекционных заболеваний костной ткани у детей. Особенности течения заболевания связаны с физиологическими характеристиками организма ребенка и незрелостью иммунной системы. Из-за активности процессов развития молочных и постоянных зубов у детей риск развития остеомиелита значительно выше. В данной статье подробно рассмотрены клинические проявления, подходы к диагностике и современные методы лечения заболевания.

Ключевые слова: одонтогенный остеомиелит, детская стоматология, воспаление челюсти, инфекция кости, диагностика, лечение.

Materials and methods

Data from pediatric dental centers on clinical presentations of the disease and treatment methods were analyzed. Diagnostic methods and treatment outcomes were compared with advanced technologies and traditional approaches.

Results

1. Pathogenesis

Odontogenic osteomyelitis often develops as a result of infection in the tooth root canal or inflammation of soft tissues. The process of resorption of primary tooth roots and eruption of permanent teeth causes pathological processes in bone tissue. Immature immunity leads to rapid spread of infection [1, 2].

2. Clinical presentation

The disease can have acute or chronic progression:

- Acute cases: Body temperature rises to 38-39°C, accompanied by jaw pain, swelling, and tooth mobility.

- Chronic cases: Characterized by necrosis of bone tissue, deformities, and soft tissue damage [3].

3. Diagnostics

Clinical examination: Pain and swelling are detected at the site of inflammation.

- Radiography: Bone tissue destruction and sequestrations are detected by X-ray.

- CT and MRI: Used for a detailed assessment of the condition of bone and soft tissues.[5]

4. Treatment

- Surgical intervention: Removal of the damaged tooth, drainage of purulent lesions, and removal of the necrotic bone.

- Medication treatment: Antibiotics (penicillin, cephalosporins) and anti-inflammatory drugs are used. [8]

- Physiotherapy: to accelerate bone regeneration.[6]

Discussion

The analysis revealed that combined methods are crucial for the diagnosis of odontogenic osteomyelitis in children. Early detection of clinical symptoms and the use of appropriate treatment methods significantly reduce mortality rates. At the same time, successful implementation of antibiotic therapy prevents disease recurrence.

Summary

Odontogenic osteomyelitis is a pathology that can be severe in children, and its effective treatment depends on early diagnosis and a comprehensive approach to the disease. Preventive measures, such as oral hygiene and the strengthening of the immune system, are of paramount importance in preventing the disease.

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